

Extension for neutrosophic vague subbisemirings of bisemirings

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Abstract. This paper introduces the idea of a neutrosophic vague subbisemiring (NSVSBS), level sets of NSVSBS, and (ρ, σ) -neutrosophic vague subbisemiring $((\rho, \sigma)$ -NSVSBS) of a bisemiring. NSVSBSs are generalizations of neutrosophic subbisemirings and SBS based on bisemirings. Let Λ be a neutrosophic vague subset in $\mathcal{B}$, we show that $\mathcal{V} = ([\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-, \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^+], [\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+], [\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^+])$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ if and only if all non empty level set $\mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$ is a SBS of $\mathcal{B}$ for $t_1, t_2, s \in [0, 1]$. In the case that Λ is a NSVSBS of a bisemiring $\mathcal{B}$ and V is the strongest neutrosophic vague relation of $\mathcal{B}$, we prove that Λ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{B}$. Let Λ be any NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$, prove that pseudo neutrosophic vague coset $(\tau\Lambda)^p$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$, for every $\tau \in \mathcal{B}$. Let $\Lambda_1, \Lambda_2, \dots, \Lambda_n$ be the family of NSVSBSs of $\mathcal{B}_1, \mathcal{B}_2, \dots, \mathcal{B}_n$ respectively. We show that $\Lambda_1 \times \Lambda_2 \times \dots \times \Lambda_n$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1 \times \mathcal{B}_2 \times \dots \times \mathcal{B}_n$. The homomorphic image of every NSVSBS is a NSVSBS. The homomorphic pre-image of every NSVSBS is a NSVSBS. Examples are provided to strengthen our results.

Keywords: subbisemiring; neutrosophic subbisemiring; neutrosophic vague bisemiring; homomorphism

1. Introduction

Due to the limitations of classical mathematics, such as fuzzy set (FS) [1] and vague set (VS) [2], mathematical theories have been developed to address uncertainty and fuzziness. In the case of uncertain or vague situations, FS introduced by Zadeh [1] is the most appropriate technique. In recent years, many hybrid fuzzy models have been developed based on FS. A generalization of FS, intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS) incorporate hesitation levels into the notion of FS, which were first proposed by Attanasov [3] in 1983. The neutrosophic set (NSS) was

proposed in 1999 by Smarandache [4]. In NSS, each proposition is estimated to have a degree of truth, an indeterminacy degree, and a falsity degree. As a result of Smarandache [5], he further generalised and expanded the theory of IFSs to include the neutrosophic model as well. A study of fuzzy semirings was initiated by Ahsan et al. [6]. Palanikumar et al. [?, ?] discussed tri-quasi-ideals and bi-quasi-ideals are natural generalizations of rings such that they constitute a natural generalization of ternary semirings, semirings and ordered semirings. In 2004, Sen et al. [17] extended the study of semirings and proposed the concept of bisemiring to further develop them. The study of vague algebra was initiated by Biswas [18] through the introduction of vague groups, vague cuts and vague normal groups. In their work, Arulmozhi et al. [19] focus on the interaction between semirings, ternary semirings and other algebraic structures. A semiring $(S, +, \cdot)$ is a non-empty set in which $(S, +)$ and $(S, \cdot)$ are semigroups such that “ $\cdot$ ” is distributive over “ $+$ ” [20]. In 1993, Ahsan et al. [6] introduced the notion of fuzzy semirings.

An introduction to bisemirings was made in 2001 by Sen et al. [21]. A bisemiring $(\mathcal{B}, \wp, \odot, \boxtimes)$ is an algebraic structure in which $(\mathcal{B}, \wp, \odot)$ and $(\mathcal{B}, \odot, \boxtimes)$ are semirings in which $(\mathcal{B}, \wp)$, $(\mathcal{B}, \odot)$ and $(\mathcal{B}, \boxtimes)$ are semigroups such that (a) $\zeta \odot (\wp \wp \tau) = (\mathfrak{R} \odot \wp) \wp (\mathfrak{R} \odot \tau)$, (b) $(\wp \wp \tau) \odot \mathfrak{R} = (\wp \odot \mathfrak{R}) \wp (\tau \odot \mathfrak{R})$, (c) $\mathfrak{R} \boxtimes (\wp \odot \tau) = (\mathfrak{R} \boxtimes \wp) \odot (\mathfrak{R} \boxtimes \tau)$ and (d) $(\wp \odot \tau) \boxtimes \mathfrak{R} = (\wp \boxtimes \mathfrak{R}) \odot (\tau \boxtimes \mathfrak{R})$ for all $\mathfrak{R}, \wp, \tau \in \mathcal{B}$ [17]. A non-empty subset Λ of a bisemiring $(\mathcal{B}, \wp, \odot, \boxtimes)$ is a subbisemiring (SBS) if and only if $\mathfrak{R} \wp \wp \in \Lambda$, $\mathfrak{R} \odot \wp \in \Lambda$ and $\mathfrak{R} \boxtimes \wp \in \Lambda$ for all $\mathfrak{R}, \wp \in \Lambda$ [21]. Palanikumar et al. discussed the various ideal structures of SBS theory and its applications [7]- [16]. However, numerous algebraic concepts had been generalized using FS theory. Fuzzy algebraic structures of semirings have been extensively investigated by Vandiver [22]. These are generalizations of rings requiring only a monoid, rather than a group, to achieve a particular additive structure and have been shown to be useful for a wide range of problems. Golan [20] and Glazek [23] have both extensively studied the application of semirings.

Bipolar fuzzy information has been applied to various algebraic structures over the past few years, like semigroups [?, 14, 15] and BCK/BCI algebras [24–27]. An application of bipolar fuzzy metric spaces was discussed by Zararsz et al. [28]. A vague soft hyperring and a vague soft hyper ideal were introduced by Selvachandran [29]. The bipolar fuzzy translation was introduced by Jun et al. [30] and BCK/BCI-algebra and its properties were investigated. A bipolar fuzzy regularity, bipolar fuzzy regular sub-algebra, a bipolar fuzzy filter, and a bipolar fuzzy closed quasi filter have been introduced into BCH algebras in [31]. In 2004, Sen et al. [17] contributed to the field of semirings by proposing bisemiring as a concept. Hussain et al. [32] defined the congruence relation between bisemirings and bisemiring homomorphisms. In addition to bisemiring, Hussain et al. [21, 32] described an algebraic structure called semiring

and congruence relations between homomorphisms and n-semirings based on this algebraic structure.

Neutrosophic vague subbisemirings (NSVSBS) are discussed here, as well as their level sets. Subbisemirings are a generalization of bisemirings, and NSVSBSs are a generalization of subbisemirings. A number of illustrative examples are provided to illustrate the theory for (ξ, τ) -NSVSBS over bisemiring theory. Following is an outline of the preliminary definitions and results presented in Section 2. The concept of a NSVSBS is introduced in Section 3. There is more information about (ξ, τ) -NSVSBS in Section 4.

2. Basic concepts

For our future studies, we will quickly review some fundamental terms in this section.

Definition 2.1. [4] A neutrosophic set (NSS) Λ in a universal set $\mathcal{U}$ is $\Lambda = \{(\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{I}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R})) : \mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{U}\}$, where $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ denotes the truth, indeterminacy and the falsity membership function, respectively. For $\langle \mathcal{T}_\Lambda, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda \rangle$ is used for the NSS $\Lambda = \{(\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{I}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R})) : \mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{U}\}$.

Definition 2.2. [4] Let $\Lambda = \langle \mathcal{T}_\Lambda, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda \rangle$ and $\Psi = \langle \mathcal{T}_\Psi, \mathcal{I}_\Psi, \mathcal{F}_\Psi \rangle$ be the two NSS of $\mathcal{U}$. Then

- (1) $\Lambda \cap \Psi = \{(\mathfrak{R}, \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})\}, \min\{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{I}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})\}, \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})\}) : \mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{U}\}$,
- (2) $\Lambda \cup \Psi = \{(\mathfrak{R}, \max\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})\}, \max\{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{I}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})\}, \min\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})\}) : \mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{U}\}$.

Definition 2.3. [4] For any NSS $\Lambda = \langle \mathcal{T}_\Lambda, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda \rangle$ of $\mathcal{U}$, we defined a (ρ, σ) -cut of as the crisp subset $\{\mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{U} : \mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}) \geq \rho, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}) \geq \rho, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}) \leq \sigma\}$ of $\mathcal{U}$.

Definition 2.4. [4] Let Λ and Ψ be two neutrosophic subsets of S . The Cartesian product of Λ and Ψ is defined as $\Lambda \times \Psi = \{((\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}), \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}), \mathcal{I}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}), \mathcal{F}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S})) : \mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S} \in S\}$, where $\mathcal{T}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}) = \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\}$, $\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}) = \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Psi(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$ and $\mathcal{F}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}) = \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Psi(\mathfrak{S})\}$.

Definition 2.5. [18] A vague set (VS) $\Lambda = (\mathcal{T}_\Lambda, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda)$ of $\mathcal{B}$ is said to be vague semiring if

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\ell_1 + \ell_2) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\ell_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\ell_2)\} \\ \mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\ell_1 \cdot \ell_2) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\ell_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\ell_2)\} \end{array} \right\}$$

and

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\ell_1 + \ell_2) \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\ell_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\ell_2)\} \\ 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\ell_1 \cdot \ell_2) \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\ell_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\ell_2)\} \end{array} \right\}.$$

for all $\ell_1, \ell_2 \in \mathcal{B}$.

Definition 2.6. [18] A VS Λ in $\mathcal{U}$. Then

- (1) A VS $\Lambda = (\mathcal{T}_\Lambda, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda)$, where $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow [0, 1], \mathcal{F}_\Lambda : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ are mappings such that $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}) \leq 1$, for all $\mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{U}$ where $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda$ and $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda$ are called true and false membership function, respectively.
- (2) The interval $[\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R})]$ is called the vague value of $\mathfrak{R}$ in Λ and it is denoted by $V_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R})$, i.e., $V_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}) = [\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R})]$.

Definition 2.7. [18] Let Λ and Ψ be the two VSs of $\mathcal{U}$. Then

- (1) Λ is contained in Ψ as $\Lambda \subseteq \Psi$ if and only if $V_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}) \leq V_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})$, i.e. $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}) \leq \mathcal{T}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})$ and $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}) \leq 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})$ for all $\mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{U}$,
- (2) the union of Λ and Ψ as $\Delta = \Lambda \cup \Psi, \mathcal{T}_\Delta = \max\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda, \mathcal{T}_\Psi\}$ and $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Delta = \max\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda, 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Psi\} = 1 - \min\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda, \mathcal{F}_\Psi\}$,
- (3) the intersection of Λ and Ψ as $\Delta = \Lambda \cap \Psi, \mathcal{T}_\Delta = \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda, \mathcal{T}_\Psi\}$ and $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Delta = \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda, 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Psi\} = 1 - \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda, \mathcal{F}_\Psi\}$.

Definition 2.8. [18] Let Λ and Ψ be any two VSs in $\mathcal{U}$. Then

- (1) $\Lambda \cap \Psi = \{(\mathfrak{R}, \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})\}, \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})\}) : \mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{U}\}$,
- (2) $\Lambda \cup \Psi = \{(\mathfrak{R}, \max\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})\}, \max\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Psi(\mathfrak{R})\}) : \mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{U}\}$,
- (3) $\square\Lambda = \{(\mathfrak{R}, \mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R})) : \mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{U}\}$,
- (4) $\diamond\Lambda = \{(\mathfrak{R}, 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R})) : \mathfrak{R} \in U\}$.

3. Neutrosophic vague subbisemirings

In all cases, assume that $\mathcal{B}$ represents a bisemiring.

Definition 3.1. A neutrosophic VS Λ of $\mathcal{B}$ is represent a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ if

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{S})\} \end{array} \right\} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \\ OR \\ \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \\ OR \\ \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{S})\} \end{array} \right\}.$$

That is,

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} \left(\begin{array}{l} \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\}, \\ 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\}, \\ 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\}, \\ 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \end{array} \right) \end{array} \right) \left(\begin{array}{l} \left(\begin{array}{l} \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \\ \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}) - \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \end{array} \right) \\ OR \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \\ \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}) - \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \end{array} \right) \\ OR \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \\ \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}) - \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \end{array} \right) \end{array} \right)$$

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} \left(\begin{array}{l} \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\}, \\ 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\}, \\ 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\}, \\ 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \end{array} \right) \end{array} \right)$$

for all $\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{B}$.

Example 3.2. Let $\mathcal{B} = \{\acute{a}, \ddot{a}, \tilde{a}, \vec{a}\}$ be the bisemiring.

$\diamond_1$	$\acute{a}$	$\ddot{a}$	$\tilde{a}$	$\vec{a}$
$\acute{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\acute{a}$
$\ddot{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\ddot{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\ddot{a}$
$\tilde{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\tilde{a}$	$\tilde{a}$
$\vec{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\ddot{a}$	$\tilde{a}$	$\vec{a}$

$\diamond_2$	$\acute{a}$	$\ddot{a}$	$\tilde{a}$	$\vec{a}$
$\acute{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\ddot{a}$	$\tilde{a}$	$\vec{a}$
$\ddot{a}$	$\ddot{a}$	$\ddot{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$
$\tilde{a}$	$\tilde{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\tilde{a}$	$\vec{a}$
$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$

$\diamond_3$	$\acute{a}$	$\ddot{a}$	$\tilde{a}$	$\vec{a}$
$\acute{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\acute{a}$
$\ddot{a}$	$\acute{a}$	$\ddot{a}$	$\tilde{a}$	$\vec{a}$
$\tilde{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$
$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$	$\vec{a}$

	$[\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\varphi), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^+(\varphi)]$	$[\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\varphi), \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\varphi)]$	$[\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\varphi), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^+(\varphi)]$
$\varphi = \acute{a}$	[0.75, 0.8]	[0.85, 0.9]	[0.2, 0.25]
$\varphi = \ddot{a}$	[0.65, 0.75]	[0.8, 0.85]	[0.25, 0.35]
$\varphi = \tilde{a}$	[0.50, 0.55]	[0.65, 0.70]	[0.45, 0.50]
$\varphi = \vec{a}$	[0.55, 0.65]	[0.75, 0.80]	[0.35, 0.45]

Clearly, Λ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$.

Theorem 3.3. *The intersection of a family of every NSVSBS^s of $\mathcal{B}$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$.*

Proof. Let $\{\mathcal{V}_i : i \in I\}$ be a collection of $NSVSBSS^s$ of $\mathcal{B}$ and $\Lambda = \bigcap_{i \in I} \mathcal{V}_i$.

Let $\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}$ in $\mathcal{B}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) &= \inf_{i \in I} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \\ &\geq \inf_{i \in I} \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ &= \min\left\{\inf_{i \in I} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R}), \inf_{i \in I} \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{S})\right\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) &= \inf_{i \in I} 1 - \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \\ &\geq \inf_{i \in I} \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ &= \min\left\{\inf_{i \in I} 1 - \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R}), \inf_{i \in I} 1 - \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{S})\right\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) &= \inf_{i \in I^-} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \\ &\geq \inf_{i \in I^-} \frac{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \\ &= \frac{\inf_{i \in I^-} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R}) + \inf_{i \in I^-} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) &= \inf_{i \in I^+} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^+(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \\ &\geq \inf_{i \in I^+} \frac{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \\ &= \frac{\inf_{i \in I^+} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \inf_{i \in I^+} \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{S})\}$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) &= \sup_{i \in I} \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \\ &\leq \sup_{i \in I} \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ &= \max\left\{\sup_{i \in I} \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R}), \sup_{i \in I} \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{S})\right\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) &= \sup_{i \in I} 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \\ &\leq \sup_{i \in I} \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ &= \max\left\{\sup_{i \in I} 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{R}), \sup_{i \in I} 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{V}_i}^-(\mathfrak{S})\right\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Hence, Λ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$.

Theorem 3.4. *If Λ and Ψ are the NSVSBS^s of $\mathcal{B}_1$ and $\mathcal{B}_2$ respectively, then $\Lambda \times \Psi$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1 \times \mathcal{B}_2$.*

Proof. Let Λ and Ψ be the NSVSBS^s of $\mathcal{B}_1$ and $\mathcal{B}_2$ respectively. Let $\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2 \in \mathcal{B}_1$ and $\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2 \in \mathcal{B}_2$. Then $(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1), (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)$ belong to $\mathcal{B}_1 \times \mathcal{B}_2$. Now

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2) &= \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2), \mathcal{T}_\Psi^-(\mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Psi^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Psi^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Psi^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}, \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2), \mathcal{T}_\Psi^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \mathcal{F}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2) &= 1 - \mathcal{F}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Psi^-(\mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Psi^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Psi^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Psi^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}, \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Psi^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{T}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{T}}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{T}}(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{T}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{T}}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{T}}(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{T}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{T}}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{T}}(\mathfrak{S})\}$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-[(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)] &= \mathcal{I}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2) + \mathcal{I}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{I}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2) + \mathcal{I}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^+[(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)] &= \mathcal{I}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^+(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda}^+(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2) + \mathcal{I}_{\Psi}^+(\mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda}^+(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_{\Lambda}^+(\mathfrak{R}_2)}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{I}_{\Psi}^+(\mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_{\Psi}^+(\mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda}^+(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_{\Psi}^+(\mathfrak{S}_1)}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda}^+(\mathfrak{R}_2) + \mathcal{I}_{\Psi}^+(\mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathcal{I}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^+(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^+(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{I}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{I}}(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{I}}(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2) \right]$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{I}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{I}}(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{I}}(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2) \right]$ and $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{I}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{I}}(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{I}}(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2) \right]$. Now

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-[(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)] &= \mathcal{F}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2), \mathcal{F}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\max\{\mathcal{F}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{F}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{F}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{\mathcal{F}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{F}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}, \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2), \mathcal{F}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{F}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-[(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)] &= 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{R}_2), 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}, \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2), 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Psi}^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^-(\mathfrak{R}_2, \mathfrak{S}_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda \times \Psi}^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{S})\}$.

Corollary 3.5. *If $\Lambda_1, \Lambda_2, \dots, \Lambda_n$ are the families of NSVSBS^s of $\mathcal{B}_1, \mathcal{B}_2, \dots, \mathcal{B}_n$ respectively, then $\Lambda_1 \times \Lambda_2 \times \dots \times \Lambda_n$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1 \times \mathcal{B}_2 \times \dots \times \mathcal{B}_n$.*

Definition 3.6. Let Λ be a neutrosophic VS in $\mathcal{B}$, the strongest neutrosophic vague relation (SNSVR) on $\mathcal{B}$, that is a NSVR on Λ is defined as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}) = \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ \mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}) = \frac{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^I(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^I(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \\ \mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}) = \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{S})\} \end{array} \right\}.$$

Theorem 3.7. *Let Λ be the NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ and V be the SNSVR of $\mathcal{B}$. Then Λ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ if and only if V is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{B}$.*

Proof. Let Λ be the NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ and V be the SNSVR of $\mathcal{B}$. Then for any $\mathfrak{R} = (\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2)$ and $\mathfrak{S} = (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)$ are in $\mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{B}$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) &= \mathcal{T}_V^- [((\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2))] \\ &= \mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}, \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2), \mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{S})\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) &= 1 - \mathcal{F}_V^- [((\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2))] \\ &= 1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}, \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2), 1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{S})\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) &= \mathcal{I}_V^-[(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)] \\ &= \mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \right] \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2) + \mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_V^+(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) &= \mathcal{I}_V^+[(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)] \\ &= \mathcal{I}_V^+(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_1)}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_2) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_2)}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \right] \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_V^+(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2) + \mathcal{I}_V^+(\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_V^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_V^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$.

Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{S})\}$, $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{S})\}$.

Conversely let us assume that V is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{B}$, then for any $\mathfrak{R} = (\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2)$ and $\mathfrak{S} = (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)$ are in $\mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{B}$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} &= \mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \mathcal{T}_V^-[(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)] \\ &= \mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \\ &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2), \mathcal{T}_V^-(\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

If $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) \leq \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)$ and $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)$. We get $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$ for all $\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1 \in \mathcal{B}$, and

$$\min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \geq \min\{\min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}$$

If $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$.

$$\min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \geq \min\{\min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}.$$

If $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$.

$$\begin{aligned} &\min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &= 1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= 1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-[(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)] \\ &= 1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \\ &\geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{S})\} \\ &= \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2), 1 - \mathcal{F}_V^-(\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

If $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) \leq 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)$ and $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1) \leq 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)$. We get $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$ for all $\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{S}_1 \in \mathcal{B}$, and $\min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \geq \min\{\min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}$.

If $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$.

$$\min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \geq \min\{\min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}.$$

If $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$.

Thus $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and

$\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \left[\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \right] &= \mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \\ &= \mathcal{I}_V^-[(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2) \diamond_1 (\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)] \\ &= \mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \\ &\geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \\ &= \frac{\mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{R}_1, \mathfrak{R}_2) + \mathcal{I}_V^-(\mathfrak{S}_1, \mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

If $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) \leq \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)$ and $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)$.

We get $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)}{2}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)}{2}$ and $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)}{2}$.

Also, $\frac{1}{2} \left[\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2) \right] \geq \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_2)}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_2)}{2} \right]$.

If $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1) \leq \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_2)$ and $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_2)$.

We get $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_1)}{2}$ and $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_1)}{2}$ and $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S}_1)}{2}$.

Thus $\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_V(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$. Similarly,

$$\max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \leq \max\{\max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}.$$

If $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) \geq \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)$ and $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)$.

We get $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$.

$$\max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \leq \max\{\max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}.$$

If $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$.

$$\max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \leq \max\{\max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}$$

If $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$.

Also, Similarly to prove that $\max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \leq \max\{\max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}$.

If $1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1) \geq 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)$ and $1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1) \geq 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)$.

We get $1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$.

$$\max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \leq \max\{\max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}.$$

If $1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$.

$$\max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_2)\} \leq \max\{\max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2)\}, \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}\}$$

$\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_2)\}$.

If $1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1) \geq 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_2 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_2)$, then $1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1 \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}_1) \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}_1)\}$. Hence, $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{S})\}$, $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_2 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_3 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Hence, Λ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$.

Theorem 3.8. *Let Λ be a NSV subset in $\mathcal{B}$. Then $\mathcal{V} = ([\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-, \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^+], [\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+], [\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^+])$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ if and only if all non empty level set $\mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$ is a SBS of $\mathcal{B}$ for $t_1, t_2, s \in [0, 1]$.*

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{V}$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$. For $t_1, t_2, s \in [0, 1]$ and $\xi_1, \xi_2 \in \mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$. We have $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1) \geq t_1, \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2) \geq t_1$ and $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1) \geq s, 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2) \geq s$ and $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1) \geq t_2, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2) \geq t_2$ and $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_1) \geq t_2, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_2) \geq t_2, 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1) \leq t_1, 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2) \leq t_1$ and $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1) \leq s, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2) \leq s$. Now, $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\} \geq t_1, 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\} \geq s$ and $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)}{2} \geq t_2, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_2)}{2} \geq t_2$ and $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\} \leq s$ and $1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\} \leq t_1$. This implies that $\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2 \in \mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$. Similarly, $\xi_1 \diamond_2 \xi_2 \in \mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$ and $\xi_1 \diamond_3 \xi_2 \in \mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$. Therefore $\mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$ is a SBS of $\mathcal{B}$, where $t_1, t_2, s \in [0, 1]$.

Conversely, assume that $\mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$ is a SBS of $\mathcal{B}$, where $t_1, t_2, s \in [0, 1]$. Suppose if there exist $\xi_1, \xi_2 \in \mathcal{B}$ such that $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) < \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}, 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) < \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) < \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)}{2}, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) < \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_2)}{2}$ and $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) > \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}, 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) > \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}$. Select $t_1, t_2, s \in [0, 1]$ such that $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) < t_1 \leq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}$ and $1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) < t_1 \leq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}$ and $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) < t_2 \leq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)}{2}$ and $\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) < t_2 \leq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_2)}{2}$ and $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) > s \geq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}, 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) > s \geq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}$. Then $\xi_1, \xi_2 \in \mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$, but $\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2 \notin \mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$. This contradicts to that $\mathcal{V}^{(t_1, t_2, s)}$ is a SBS of $\mathcal{B}$. Hence, $\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}, 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)}{2}, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \geq \frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_1) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\xi_2)}{2}$ and $\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}$ and $1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1 \diamond_1 \xi_2) \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_1), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\xi_2)\}$. Similarly, $\diamond_2$ and $\diamond_3$ cases. Hence, $\mathcal{V} = ([\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-, \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^+], [\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-, \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+], [\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-, \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^+])$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$.

Definition 3.9. Let Λ be any NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ and $\tau \in \mathcal{B}$. Then the pseudo NSV coset $(\tau\Lambda)^p$ is defined by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\tau\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T)^p(\mathfrak{R}) = p(\tau)\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}), \\ (\tau\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^I)^p(\mathfrak{R}) = p(\tau)\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^I(\mathfrak{R}), \\ (\tau\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F)^p(\mathfrak{R}) = p(\tau)\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{R}) \end{array} \right\}.$$

That is,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}) = p(\tau)\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \quad 1 - (\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}) = p(\tau)(1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)(\mathfrak{R}), \\ (\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}) = p(\tau)\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \quad (\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+)^p(\mathfrak{R}) = p(\tau)\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}), \\ (\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}) = p(\tau)\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \quad 1 - (\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}) = p(\tau)(1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)(\mathfrak{R}) \end{array} \right\}$$

each $\mathfrak{R} \in \mathcal{B}$ and for any non-empty set $p \in P$.

Theorem 3.10. *Let Λ be any NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$, then the pseudo NSV coset $(\tau\Lambda)^p$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$.*

Proof. Let Λ be any NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ and for each $\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{B}$. Now, $(\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) = p(\tau) \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq p(\tau) \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} = \min\{p(\tau) \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), p(\tau) \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} = \min\{(\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}), (\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Thus $(\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{(\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}), (\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and $1 - (\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) = p(\tau) (1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S})) \geq p(\tau) \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} = \min\{p(\tau) (1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R})), p(\tau) (1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}))\} = \min\{1 - (\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - (\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Thus $1 - (\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{1 - (\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - (\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Now, $(\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) = p(\tau) \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq p(\tau) \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \right] = \frac{p(\tau) \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}) + p(\tau) \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2} = \frac{(\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}) + (\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$. Thus $(\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{(\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}) + (\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$ and $(\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) = p(\tau) \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq p(\tau) \left[\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \right] = \frac{p(\tau) \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}) + p(\tau) \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2} = \frac{(\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+)^p(\mathfrak{R}) + (\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+)^p(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$. Thus $(\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{(\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+)^p(\mathfrak{R}) + (\tau\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+)^p(\mathfrak{S})}{2}$. Now, $(\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) = p(\tau) \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \leq p(\tau) \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} = \max\{p(\tau) \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), p(\tau) \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} = \max\{(\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}), (\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Thus $(\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{(\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}), (\tau\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{S})\}$ and $1 - (\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) = p(\tau) (1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S})) \leq p(\tau) \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})\} = \max\{p(\tau) (1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R})), p(\tau) (1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}))\} = \max\{1 - (\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - (\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Thus $1 - (\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R} \diamond_1 \mathfrak{S}) \leq \max\{1 - (\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - (\tau\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-)^p(\mathfrak{S})\}$. Similarly, $\diamond_2$ and $\diamond_3$ cases. Hence, $(\tau\Lambda)^p$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$.

Definition 3.11. Let $(\mathcal{B}_1, \varnothing_1, \varnothing_2, \varnothing_3)$ and $(\mathcal{B}_2, \varnothing_1, \varnothing_2, \varnothing_3)$ be the bisemirings. Let $\Upsilon : \mathcal{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_2$ and Λ be an NSVSBS in $\mathcal{B}_1$, V be an NSVSBS in $\Upsilon(\mathcal{B}_1) = \mathcal{B}_2$, the image of VS is defined as $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{U}(V)}(l_2) = [T_{\mathcal{U}(V)}^-(l_2), 1 - F_{\mathcal{U}(V)}^-(l_2)], [I_{\mathcal{U}(V)}^-(l_2), I_{\mathcal{U}(V)}^+(l_2)], [F_{\mathcal{U}(V)}^-(l_2), 1 - T_{\mathcal{U}(V)}^-(l_2)]$ where $T_{\mathcal{U}(V)}^-(l_2) = T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(l_2))$, $I_{\mathcal{U}(V)}^-(l_2) = I_V^-(\mathcal{U}(l_2))$, $I_{\mathcal{U}(V)}^+(l_2) = I_V^+(\mathcal{U}(l_2))$ and $F_{\mathcal{U}(V)}^-(l_2) = F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(l_2))$.

Definition 3.12. Let $(\mathcal{B}_1, \varnothing_1, \varnothing_2, \varnothing_3)$ and $(\mathcal{B}_2, \varnothing_1, \varnothing_2, \varnothing_3)$ be the bisemirings. Let $\mathcal{U} : \mathcal{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_2$ be any function. Let V be a VS in $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{B}_1) = \mathcal{B}_2$. Then the inverse image of V , $\mathcal{U}^{-1}$ is the VS in $\mathcal{B}_1$ by $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}(l_1) = [T_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}^-(l_1), 1 - F_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}^-(l_1)], [I_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}^-(l_1), I_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}^+(l_1)], [F_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}^-(l_1), 1 - T_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}^-(l_1)]$, where $T_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}^-(l_1) = T_V^-(\mathcal{U}^{-1}(l_1))$, $I_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}^-(l_1) = I_V^-(\mathcal{U}^{-1}(l_1))$, $I_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}^+(l_1) = I_V^+(\mathcal{U}^{-1}(l_1))$, $F_{\mathcal{U}^{-1}(V)}^-(l_1) = F_V^-(\mathcal{U}^{-1}(l_1))$.

Theorem 3.13. *Every homomorphic image of NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_2$.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{U} : \mathcal{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_2$ be a homomorphism. Now, $\mathcal{U}(l_1 \varnothing_1 l_2) = \mathcal{U}(l_1) \varnothing_1 \mathcal{U}(l_2)$, $\mathcal{U}(l_1 \varnothing_2 l_2) = \mathcal{U}(l_1) \varnothing_2 \mathcal{U}(l_2)$ and $\mathcal{U}(l_1 \varnothing_3 l_2) = \mathcal{U}(l_1) \varnothing_3 \mathcal{U}(l_2)$ for all $l_1, l_2 \in \mathcal{B}_1$. Let $V = \mathcal{U}(\Lambda)$, Λ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1$. Let $\mathcal{U}(l_1), \mathcal{U}(l_2) \in \mathcal{B}_2$, $T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(l_1) \varnothing_1 \mathcal{U}(l_2)) \geq T_\Lambda^-(l_1 \varnothing_1 l_2) \geq \min\{T_\Lambda^-(l_1), T_\Lambda^-(l_2)\} = \min\{T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(l_1)), T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(l_2))\}$ and $1 - F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(l_1) \varnothing_1 \mathcal{U}(l_2)) \geq 1 - F_\Lambda^-(l_1 \varnothing_1 l_2) \geq \min\{1 - F_\Lambda^-(l_1), 1 - F_\Lambda^-(l_2)\} =$

$\min\{1 - F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)), 1 - F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_2))\}$. Thus $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_1), \mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_1), \mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_1), \mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)\}$. Now, $I_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \geq I_\Lambda^-(\ell_1\mathcal{D}_1\ell_2) \geq \frac{I_\Lambda^-(\ell_1)+I_\Lambda^-(\ell_2)}{2} = \frac{I_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1))+I_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_2))}{2}$ and $I_V^+(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \geq I_\Lambda^+(\ell_1\mathcal{D}_1\ell_2) \geq \frac{I_\Lambda^+(\ell_1)+I_\Lambda^+(\ell_2)}{2} = \frac{I_V^+(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1))+I_V^+(\mathcal{U}(\ell_2))}{2}$. Thus $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)+\mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)}{2}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_1), \mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_1), \mathcal{V}_V^T\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)\}$. Now, $F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \leq F_\Lambda^-(\ell_1\mathcal{D}_1\ell_2) \leq \max\{F_\Lambda^-(\ell_1), F_\Lambda^-(\ell_2)\} = \max\{F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)), F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_2))\}$ and $1 - T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \leq 1 - T_\Lambda^-(\ell_1\mathcal{D}_1\ell_2) \leq \max\{1 - T_\Lambda^-(\ell_1), 1 - T_\Lambda^-(\ell_2)\} = \max\{1 - T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)), 1 - T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\ell_2))\}$. Thus $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F\mathcal{U}(\ell_1), \mathcal{V}_V^F\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F\mathcal{U}(\ell_1), \mathcal{V}_V^F\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{U}(\ell_1)\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F\mathcal{U}(\ell_1), \mathcal{V}_V^F\mathcal{U}(\ell_2)\}$. Hence, V is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_2$.

Theorem 3.14. *Every homomorphic pre-image of NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_2$ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1$.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{U} : \mathcal{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_2$ and $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S}), \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{S}) = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S})$ and $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{S}) = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S})$ for all $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{B}_1$. Let $V = \mathcal{U}(\Lambda)$, where V is any NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_2$. Let $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{B}_1$. Now, $T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) = T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S})) = T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S})) \geq \min\{T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})), T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S}))\} = \min\{T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}), T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{S})\}$. Thus $T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) \geq \min\{T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}), T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{S})\}$ and $1 - F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) = 1 - F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S})) = 1 - F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S})) \geq \min\{1 - F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})), 1 - F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S}))\} = \min\{1 - F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}), 1 - F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{S})\}$. Thus $1 - F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) \geq \min\{1 - F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}), 1 - F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{S})\}$. Hence, $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{S})\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{S})\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{S}) \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^T(\mathcal{S})\}$. Now, $I_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) = I_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S})) = I_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S})) \geq \frac{I_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}))+I_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S}))}{2} = \frac{I_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R})+I_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{S})}{2}$. Thus $I_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) \geq \frac{I_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R})+I_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{S})}{2}$ and $I_\Lambda^+(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) = I_V^+(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S})) = I_V^+(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S})) \geq \frac{I_V^+(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}))+I_V^+(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S}))}{2} = \frac{I_\Lambda^+(\mathcal{R})+I_\Lambda^+(\mathcal{S})}{2}$. Thus $I_\Lambda^+(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) \geq \frac{I_\Lambda^+(\mathcal{R})+I_\Lambda^+(\mathcal{S})}{2}$. Hence, $\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathcal{R})+\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathcal{S})}{2}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathcal{R})+\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathcal{S})}{2}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{S}) \geq \frac{\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathcal{R})+\mathcal{V}_V^I(\mathcal{S})}{2}$. Now, $F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) = F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S})) = F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S})) \leq \max\{F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})), F_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S}))\} = \max\{F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}), F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{S})\}$. Thus $F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) \leq \max\{F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}), F_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{S})\}$ and $1 - T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) = 1 - T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S})) = 1 - T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S})) \leq \max\{1 - T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})), 1 - T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S}))\} = \max\{1 - T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}), 1 - T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{S})\}$. Thus $1 - T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) \leq \max\{1 - T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{R}), 1 - T_\Lambda^-(\mathcal{S})\}$. Hence, $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{S})\}$. Similarly, $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{S})\}$ and $\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{S}) \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{R}), \mathcal{V}_V^F(\mathcal{S})\}$. Hence, Λ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1$.

Theorem 3.15. *If $\mathcal{U} : \mathcal{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_2$ is a homomorphism, then $\mathcal{U}(\Lambda_{(t_1, t_2, s)})$ is a level SBS of NSVSBS V of $\mathcal{B}_2$.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{U} : \mathcal{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_2$ be a homomorphism and $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}) = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S}), \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{S}) = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S})$ and $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{S}) = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{S})$ for all $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{S} \in \mathcal{B}_1$. Let $V = \mathcal{U}(\Lambda)$, Λ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1$. By Theorem 3.13, V is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_2$. Let $\Lambda_{(t_1, t_2, s)}$ be any level SBS of Λ . Suppose that $\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{S} \in \Lambda_{(t_1, t_2, s)}$. Then $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{S}), \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{S})$ and $\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R}\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{S}) \in \Lambda_{(t_1, t_2, s)}$. Now, $T_V^-(\mathcal{U}(\mathcal{R})) =$

$T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) \geq t_1, T_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) = T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S}) \geq t_1$. Thus $T_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \geq T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) \geq t_1$ and $1 - F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) = 1 - F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) \geq s, 1 - F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) = 1 - F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S}) \geq s$. Thus $1 - F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \geq 1 - F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) \geq s$. Now, $I_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) = I_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) \geq t_2, I_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) = I_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S}) \geq t_2$. Thus $I_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \geq I_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) \geq t_2$ and $I_V^{+}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) = I_{\Lambda}^{+}(\mathfrak{R}) \geq t_2, I_V^{+}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) = I_{\Lambda}^{+}(\mathfrak{S}) \geq t_2$. Thus $I_V^{+}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \geq I_{\Lambda}^{+}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) \geq t_2$. Now, $F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) = F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) \leq s, F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) = F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S}) \leq s$. Thus $F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \leq F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) \leq s$ and $1 - T_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) = 1 - T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) \leq t_1, 1 - T_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) = 1 - T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S}) \leq t_1$. Thus $1 - T_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \leq 1 - T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) \leq t_1$, for all $\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S}) \in \mathcal{B}_2$. Similarly to prove other operations. Hence proved.

Theorem 3.16. *If $\mathcal{U} : \mathcal{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_2$ is any homomorphism, then $\Lambda_{(t_1, t_2, s)}$ is a level SBS of NSVSBS Λ of $\mathcal{B}_1$.*

Proof. Let $\mathcal{U} : \mathcal{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{B}_2$ be a homomorphism and $\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) = \mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S}), \mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_2\mathfrak{S}) = \mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_2\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})$ and $\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_3\mathfrak{S}) = \mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_3\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})$ for all $\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{B}_1$. Let $V = \mathcal{U}(\Lambda)$, V is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_2$. By Theorem 3.14, Λ is a NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1$. Let $\mathcal{U}(\Lambda_{(t_1, t_2, s)})$ be a level SBS of V . Suppose that $\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S}) \in \mathcal{U}(\Lambda_{(t_1, t_2, s)})$. Then $\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}), \mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_2\mathfrak{S})$ and $\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_3\mathfrak{S}) \in \mathcal{U}(\Lambda_{(t_1, t_2, s)})$. Now, $T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) = T_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) \geq t_1, T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S}) = T_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \geq t_1$. Thus $T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}), T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S})\} \geq t_1$ and $1 - F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) = 1 - F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) \geq s, 1 - F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S}) = 1 - F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \geq s$. Thus $1 - F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) \geq \min\{1 - F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S})\} \geq s$. Now, $I_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) = I_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) \geq t_2, I_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S}) = I_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \geq t_2$. Thus $I_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{I_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) + I_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \geq t_2$ and $I_{\Lambda}^{+}(\mathfrak{R}) = I_V^{+}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) \geq t_2, I_{\Lambda}^{+}(\mathfrak{S}) = I_V^{+}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \geq t_2$. Thus $I_{\Lambda}^{+}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) \geq \frac{I_{\Lambda}^{+}(\mathfrak{R}) + I_{\Lambda}^{+}(\mathfrak{S})}{2} \geq t_2$. Now, $F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) = F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) \leq s, F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S}) = F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \leq s$. Thus $F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) = F_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \leq \max\{F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}), F_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S})\} \leq s$ and $1 - T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}) = 1 - T_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})) \leq t_1, 1 - T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S}) = 1 - T_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \leq t_1$. Thus $1 - T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}) = 1 - T_V^{-}(\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{R})\mathcal{D}_1\mathcal{U}(\mathfrak{S})) \leq \max\{1 - T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - T_{\Lambda}^{-}(\mathfrak{S})\} \leq t_1$, for all $\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{B}_1$. Similarly to prove other two operations. Hence proved.

4. (ρ, σ) -Neutrosophic vague SBSs

We discuss about (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS and $(\rho, \sigma) \in [0, 1]$ be such that $0 \leq \rho < \sigma \leq 1$.

Definition 4.1. Let Λ be any NSVS of $\mathcal{B}$ is called a (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ if

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \max\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \\ \max\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_2\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \\ \max\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_3\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \end{array} \right\} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \max\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_1\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\left\{\frac{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \sigma\right\} \\ OR \\ \max\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_2\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\left\{\frac{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \sigma\right\} \\ OR \\ \max\{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}\mathcal{D}_3\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\left\{\frac{\mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_{\Lambda}^T(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \sigma\right\} \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_1\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \\ \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_2\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \\ \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_3\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \leq \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^{\mathcal{F}}(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \end{array} \right\}.$$

That is,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left(\begin{array}{l} \max\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_1\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\}, \\ \max\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_1\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \max\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_2\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\}, \\ \max\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_2\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \max\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_3\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\}, \\ \max\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_3\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\{1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \max\{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_1\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\left\{\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \sigma\right\} \\ \max\{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_1\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\left\{\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}) - \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \sigma\right\} \end{array} \right) \\ \text{OR} \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \max\{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_2\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\left\{\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \sigma\right\} \\ \max\{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_2\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\left\{\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}) - \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \sigma\right\} \end{array} \right) \\ \text{OR} \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \max\{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_3\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\left\{\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \sigma\right\} \\ \max\{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_3\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \geq \min\left\{\frac{\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}) - \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \sigma\right\} \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \min\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_1\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\}, \\ \min\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_1\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \min\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_2\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\}, \\ \min\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_2\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \end{array} \right) \\ \left(\begin{array}{l} \min\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_3\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\}, \\ \min\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}\diamond_3\mathfrak{S}), \rho\} \leq \max\{1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{R}), 1 - \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \end{array} \right) \end{array} \right)$$

for all $\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S} \in \mathcal{B}$.

Example 4.2. By Example 3.2,

	$[\mathcal{T}_\Lambda^-(\varphi), \mathcal{T}_\Lambda^+(\varphi)]$	$[\mathcal{I}_\Lambda^-(\varphi), \mathcal{I}_\Lambda^+(\varphi)]$	$[\mathcal{F}_\Lambda^-(\varphi), \mathcal{F}_\Lambda^+(\varphi)]$
$\varphi = \dot{a}$	[0.65, 0.70]	[0.55, 0.65]	[0.3, 0.35]
$\varphi = \ddot{a}$	[0.6, 0.65]	[0.50, 0.60]	[0.35, 0.40]
$\varphi = \tilde{a}$	[0.35, 0.40]	[0.25, 0.30]	[0.60, 0.65]
$\varphi = \vec{a}$	[0.45, 0.55]	[0.40, 0.50]	[0.45, 0.55]

Clearly, Λ is a (0.25, 0.85) NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$.

Theorem 4.3. *The intersection of a family of every (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS^s is a (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS.*

Proof. The proof is similar to Theorem 3.3.

Theorem 4.4. *If Λ and Ψ are any two (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS^s of $\mathcal{B}_1$ and $\mathcal{B}_2$ respectively, then $\Lambda \times \Psi$ is a (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1 \times \mathcal{B}_2$.*

Proof. The proof is similar to Theorem 3.4.

Corollary 4.5. *If $\Lambda_1, \Lambda_2, \dots, \Lambda_n$ are the families of (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS^s of $\mathcal{B}_1, \mathcal{B}_2, \dots, \mathcal{B}_n$ respectively, then $\Lambda_1 \times \Lambda_2 \times \dots \times \Lambda_n$ is a (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1 \times \mathcal{B}_2 \times \dots \times \mathcal{B}_n$.*

Definition 4.6. Let Λ be a (ρ, σ) -NSVS in $\mathcal{B}$, the (ρ, σ) -SNSVR on $\mathcal{B}$. ie) (ρ, σ) -NSVR on Λ is V given by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}), \rho\} = \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \\ \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}), \rho\} = \min\left\{\frac{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{R}) + \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^T(\mathfrak{S})}{2}, \sigma\right\} \\ \min\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{S}), \rho\} = \max\{\mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{R}), \mathcal{V}_\Lambda^F(\mathfrak{S}), \sigma\} \end{array} \right\}.$$

Theorem 4.7. *Let Λ be a (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ and V be the (ρ, σ) -SNSVR of $\mathcal{B}$. Then Λ is a (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}$ if and only if V is a (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{B}$.*

Proof. A similar proof is given in Theorem 3.7.

Theorem 4.8. *A homomorphic image of (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1$ is a (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_2$.*

Proof. A similar proof is given in Theorem 3.13.

Theorem 4.9. *A homomorphic pre-image of (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_2$ is a (ρ, σ) -NSVSBS of $\mathcal{B}_1$.*

Proof. A similar proof is given in Theorem 3.14.

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